

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF HYALURONIC ACID MICRO-BEAD AND HYDROGEL IMPLANT CROSS-LINKED BY DIVINYLSULFONE

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1 General Introduction

Hyaluronic acid (HA), a common component of synovial fluid and extracellular matrix, is a linear high molar mass, natural polysaccharide composed of alternating (1→4)-β linked D-glucuronic and (1→3)-β linked N-acetyl-D-glucosamine residues [1]. HA is reported to be a group of substances known as glycosaminoglycans, being structurally the most simple among them, the only one not covalently associated with a core protein and the only non-sulfated one. Higher molar mass of HA (10⁷ Da) and its associated unique viscoelastic and rheological properties make HA to play important physiological roles in living organisms and make it an attractive biomaterials for various medical applications [1-8]. However, poor mechanical properties and rapid degradation of HA limit broader ranges of clinical applications [8].

Hydrogels are ideal materials for soft tissue augmentation due to their regeneration properties of various tissues, mechanical properties, softness, oxygen permeability, similarities the body's own highly hydrated composition and excellent biocompatibilities [8]. Among natural polymers, such as collagen, gelatin, fibrin, alginic acid, chitosan and HA, cross-link-stabilized HA is highly acknowledged as a naturally derived injectable filler due to its longevity of correction, a reduced risk of immunogenicity and hypersensitivity, and its controllable mechanical and degradation properties [2,3,8]. HA molecule is stabilized to produce cross-linked gel suitable for soft-tissue implantation, resulting in improving its resistance to enzymatic degradation within the dermis without compromising its biocompatibility [1-8]. They demonstrated their efficacy in correcting aesthetic defects such as congenital or hypovolumetries, nasolabial furrows, forehead, glabella wrinkles,

cheekbone, chin hypovolumetry and lip augmentation [2-7].

To improve the mechanical properties and control the degradation rate, HA can be chemically modified. Chemical modification of HA typically involves the carboxylic acid groups and/or the alcohol groups of its backbone. The carboxylic acid or alcohol groups have been modified by esterification or cross-linking to improve the mechanical properties and degradation behavior of HA hydrogels [8]. In the present study, divinyl sulfone was chosen as the cross-linking molecule because it is biocompatible and hydrophilic [9]. HA hydrogels cross-linked by divinyl sulfone (HAHs) were prepared by immersing the micro-beads in phosphate buffered saline solution (NaH₂PO₄) [9-11]. There are several methods in preparing the micro-beads, such as suspension [12], emulsion [3], dispersion [13] and solution polymerization [14]. In the present study, a modified solution polymerization plus atomization were employed to fabricate the micro-beads [9-11]. Micro-beads were firstly prepared for the synthesis of HAHs by collecting them into a solution mixture of divinyl sulfone and 2-methyl-1-propanol. Then, the cross-linked micro-beads were immersed in ethanol to clean the beads by removing impurities such as divinyl sulfone and 2-methyl-1-propanol. The micro-beads were then immersed in phosphate buffered saline solution to obtain HAHs. As the size of micro-beads is decreased, the specific surface area is dramatically increased, resulting in higher mechanical properties and longer lifetime. In addition, the porous surface can be obtained by cleaning the micro-beads in ethanol. Morphology of micro-beads and cytotoxicity of HAHs are evaluated to assess biocompatibility of the gels before implantation.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

HA solutions of 0.5 wt% concentration were prepared by dissolving a 0.5 g of sodium hyaluronate ($M_w=1 \times 10^6$ Da, Shiseido Co., Japan) in 100 mL of 0.05 mol/L NaOH at room temperature. A pH in the range of 12 to 14 was achieved by adding 0.4 mL of 10 mol/L NaOH to the HA solution. Then, the HA solution was placed in a solution hopper attached to the syringe pump and fed into the delivery tube at a flow rate of 0.005 mL/min. Micro-beads were collected into a solution mixture of 0.2 mL of divinyl sulfone ($\geq 98\%$, Sigma and Aldrich, Germany) and 98 mL of 2-methyl-1-propanol (99%, Aldrich), followed by a stirring process (200~400 rpm) for 10~25 h at room temperature. Then, the cross-linked micro-beads were immersed in ethanol for 0.5 h to clean the beads by removing impurities such as divinyl sulfone and 2-methyl-1-propanol. After at least 3-time cleaning in ethanol, micro-beads were filtered through the 200 mesh sieve and then dried for 2 h at 60°C in vacuum (20 torr). The as-dried micro-beads were immersed in 100 mL of phosphate buffered saline solution (NaH_2PO_4) to obtain HAHs [9]. Surface microstructure of the micro-beads was evaluated using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, Hitachi, S-3000H, Japan). Prior to cleaning in ethanol, the beads were sieved through the 200 mesh, cleaned in distilled water for 15 min to limit further cross-linking and then dried in vacuum. Cleaned micro-beads were also prepared for the comparison. The presence of divinyl sulfone (cross linker) after cleaning in ethanol may be adverse and allergic reactions of the HAHs because they have been used within the dermis for several months. The presence of the cross-linker residue in HAHs after cleaning is evaluated by using a gas chromatography (GC, Agilent, HP6890N, USA). Four standard stock solutions of 10 mg/L, 250 mg/L, 500 mg/L and 1,000 mg/L were prepared.

2.2 Cytotoxicity

The extract test method was conducted on the test article to evaluate the potential of cytotoxicity on the basis of International Organization for Standardization (ISO 10993-5). A test article (hydrogel) was extracted aseptically in single

strength Minimum Essential Medium (1X MEM) with serum. The ratio of hydrogel to extraction vehicle was 4g/20 mL. The test sample was used in the test within 24 h after the completion of the preparation. The test extract was placed onto three separate confluent monolayers of L-929 (NCTC Clone 929, ATCC, USA) mouse fibroblast cells propagated in 5% CO_2 . For this test, confluent monolayer cells were trypsinized and seeded in 10 cm^2 wells (35 mm dishes). Simultaneously, triplicates of reagent control, negative control, positive control were placed onto the confluent L-929 monolayers. The wells were incubated at 37°C in 5% CO_2 for 48 h. All monolayers were incubated at 37°C in the presence of 5% CO_2 for 48 h. After incubation, the morphological change of the cell was examined under microscope to assess the biological reaction.

3 Results and Discussion

SEM results of micro-beads cross-linked for 20 h, as shown in Fig. 1, implied that the shape of the surface was changed from smooth-like capsular membrane to porous surface after cleaning in ethanol probably due to the elimination of cross-linker. The presence of the cross-linker (divinyl sulfone) was observed on the outer surface of the uncleaned HA micro-beads, as shown in Fig. 2. The arrows in Fig. 2 indicate the residual cross-linker. The residual of divinyl sulfone on the surface of beads was further examined by using GC. No divinyl sulfone peaks were detected for the HAHs prepared by the cleaning treatment in ethanol, as depicted in Fig. 3. It suggested that the cleaning process is very crucial for the synthesis of HAHs.

Longer cross-linking time caused the larger size of micro-beads, which is in good agreement with the previous result [10]. As the cross-linking time rose from 10 h to 25 h, the mean diameter of micro-beads was increased from 87 to 101 μm , as demonstrated in Figs. 4 and 5. However, the optimum condition of micro-beads for the HAHs warrant further studies.

A cytotoxicity test determines whether a product or compound will have any toxic effect on living cells. The confluence of the monolayer was recorded as (+) if present and (-) if absent. Under the conditions of this study, the 1X MEM test extract showed no evidence of causing cell lysis or toxicity as listed in

Fig. 1. SEM images of HA micro-beads (a) before and (b) after cleaning in ethanol. Note that the micro-beads were cross-linked for 20 h.

Fig. 2. SEM images of HA micro-beads before cleaning at different magnification. Note that the arrows indicate the presence of cross-linker.

Fig. 3. GC graphs of (a) standard solution of the divinyl sulfone and (b) the HAHs. Note that the HAHs were cross-linked by divinyl sulfone for 20 h.

Fig. 4. SEM images of HA micro-beads prepared by different cross-linking time: (a) 10 h, (b) 15 h, (c) 20 h and (d) 25 h, respectively.

Fig. 5. Effect of cross-linking time on mean diameter of HA micro-beads.

Table 1. For the test to be valid (ISO 10993-5), the reagent control and the negative control must have had a reactivity of none (cytotoxicity scale 0) and the positive control must have been severely cytotoxic (cytotoxicity scale 3). The reagent control and negative control showed no cytotoxicity and the positivity control showed cytotoxicity in more than 75% cells as expected. The reactivity of the test sample was determined to be none. Therefore, HAHs are likely to be suitable filler for soft tissue augmentation due to the lack of cytotoxicity.

Table 1. L-929 cytotoxicity test results.

well	confluent Monolayer	% lysis	reactivity	cytotoxicity scale
test	+	0	none	0
reagent	+	0	none	0
negative	+	0	none	0
positive	-	0	N/A	3

4 Conclusions

HAHs were synthesized by immersing the micro-beads in phosphate buffered saline solution. As the cross-linking time is increased from 10 to 25 h, the mean diameter of beads rose from 87 to 101 μm . Cleaning treatment of micro-beads was performed in ethanol to eliminate the residual cross-linker after the reaction. Although smooth surface of the micro-beads was observed as an indication of residual divinyl sulfone before the cleaning treatment, no divinyl sulfone on the porous surface of cleaned beads was detected regardless of cross-linking time, suggesting that cleaning process is crucial for the synthesis of HAHs for drug deliver, drug elution and scaffold. A cytotoxicity test of the HAHs was examined. No evidence of causing cell lysis or toxicity was detected. The reactivity of the HAHs was found to be none. Therefore, HAHs are likely to be suitable filler for soft tissue augmentation due to the noncytotoxicity.

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